

A Transmedia History Approach to Studying the Cultural Politics of Software Interfaces, 1977-1995

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In my paper, I explore how a transmedia approach can play a crucial role in developing a conceptual framework for historical research on software interfaces. I am currently designing such a framework for my upcoming research project, *INTERFACE POLITICS: Evolution of Software Interfaces and the Politics of the Imagined Computer User, 1977–1995*. This project aims to analyze how software interfaces from 1977 to 1995—including operating systems, productivity software, utilities, edutainment, and games—embedded computer users within power/knowledge dynamics and either reinforced or challenged cultural norms associated with the "imagined user."

The UI functions as a screen-based, aesthetic representation of a computer's functionality (Andersen, Pold, 2011). Additionally, the UI enables the computer to simulate itself (Krapp, 2024) by providing users with an intelligible set of abstractions (such as files and folders) and presenting possible actions in a comprehensible manner. My project adopts a historical approach, critically analyzing the evolution of personal computing from 1977 to 1995, with a focus on the changing politics of design language in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). I conceptualize UIs as integrated systems that merge discourse, visual representation, and technical functionality, exploring the interplay between these domains. My research is primarily grounded in critical software studies (Fuller, 2008; Mackenzie, 2006), a field that emerged within the broader framework of media archaeology. To enhance this framework, I incorporate selected concepts from Science and Technology Studies (STS), media history, and design studies.

I aim to outline how a transmedia approach can be used to build a research toolset that connects theory development with empirical research. First, I argue that a software interface is a form of media in itself. As a result, the history of interfaces should receive more attention and theoretical consideration, similar to other "media histories." While there is a body of studies on the contemporary digital environment in terms of "interface culture" (e.g., Paulsen, 2017; Hookway, 2014; Callahan, 2004; Jørgensen, 2014), scholars paid very little attention to critically examining the historical development of UIs. Moreover, these aforementioned works can often be interpreted as examples of research focused on monomedia units.

I explain how I adopt a transmedia approach in designing an exploratory project that develops theory through extensive empirical research involving diverse media objects. My project goes beyond analyzing the program itself to investigate the functionalities and cultural significance of software interfaces. In doing so, I address the issue of screen essentialism—a "monomedia perspective" often seen in works on software history, including game studies research. Much of the existing scholarship and popular discourse focuses on the aesthetics and internal organization of the screen, which is central to the interface. However, studies that address the historical trajectory of software interfaces often pay little attention to concepts like 'transcending monomedia units,' as mentioned in the CFP, or to the various forms of circulation that occur between media.

Surprisingly, there is very little empirically based theoretical consideration of computers as a medium. While there is a substantial body of literature discussing computers as tools for accessing digital media such as movies and music, these discussions often focus on the interfaces of programs used to access such media. However, relatively little scholarly attention has been devoted to studying the histories of interaction with computers as a medium in their own right. This research gap is evident in the relative lack of studies that bridge the fields of the history of computing and media history.

Historically, computer interfaces functioned as transmedia objects, visually representing programs on the screen. This visualization extensively used references to the design conventions in other media, but also extensively used conventions from office work. To ensure these interfaces were fully functional and widely adopted, they relied on various supporting materials. These included user manuals, keyboard overlays, reference cards, and favorable reviews in computer magazines. Visual elements such as box art, advertisements, and TV commercials also played a critical role. Furthermore, third-party books and magazine guides often offered additional support, occasionally revealing undocumented interface features.

I argue that software interfaces should be investigated as mediums interconnected with various objects. These objects should not be seen merely as historical sources for studying the history of software but as integral elements of the software itself. My application of the transmedia approach is informed by several corresponding and complementary frameworks, including John Law's study (2002) on decentering objects in STS scholarship, selected works on transmedia by Kinder and McPherson (2014), and recent calls for theoretically informed research in the history of computing by Abbate and Dick (2022).

In my paper, I present the key ideas that form the theoretical framework and design of the empirical research for my project. My research agenda aligns with the remark included in the CFP, which emphasizes moving away from "accumulating histories of different media" and instead focusing on "the elements that bridge them" [Transmedia CFP]. My research involves the emulation of a sample of legacy programs to better understand their functionalities. However, the insights into design language and human-computer interaction systems derived from emulation-based research are closely connected to four key areas. These include the use of historical sources beyond the program itself to explore how the interface existed within the broader media landscape of its era.

Here, I outline the key research areas of my project that correspond to the field of transmedia research

1. Decentering interfaces.

Here, I demonstrate the extent to which the software user interface was embedded within print culture. Contemporary interfaces are, so to say, largely self-sustained, incorporating tutorials, tooltips, and other user aids directly within the interface itself. However, historically, software was accompanied by extensive collections of printed materials. The most obvious of these artefacts was the user manual. Beyond that, users were often provided with other materials, such as reference cards and technical documentation. In addition to official documents, there was—and still is—a robust industry of third-party books providing users with additional knowledge. For example, at this moment, I have collected more than fifty third-party books that teach users how to operate or design programs for various iterations of the Mac OS and Windows 95.

I also design an analysis of how software interfaces and their claimed innovativeness are portrayed in other media. Specifically, I aim to conduct a critical discourse analysis of the language used in software reviews in the computer press to highlight positive or negative impressions of user interfaces. 'Software critics,' as magazine editors referred to themselves, developed a specific vocabulary and set of conventions in their reviews to emphasize the strengths or weaknesses of an interface.

2. Connecting interfaces to broader ideas of how users should interact with computer as a medium.

This research area focuses on selecting and deconstructing several broad ideas and more specific design principles of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). These concepts have played a pivotal role in shaping and negotiating the role of the user interface as a central element in computer-based media ecosystems. For example, I can reference a seminal work that deconstructs the politics surrounding the concept of "user-friendliness" (Black, 2022). Similarly, Rachel Plotnick, in her study *Pushing the Button Across the Twentieth Century*, argues that not only the button itself but also the designed pleasures, experiences of control, and agency associated with pushing a button across various media and infrastructures played a pivotal role in shaping modernity in the twentieth century. Of course,

interacting with a user interface often involves similar pleasures of control of clicking buttons on-screen or pressing the ENTER key. Drawing from professional literature on HCI and software criticism, my research deconstructs the role of these interactions in computer as a medium.

3. How interfaces represent office ecosystems?

This focal point of my research deconstructs the key influence of office-related ideas and objects on how interfaces are designed to integrate into the everyday lives of users. Office culture is not a medium itself, but as Haigh (2012) noted, it was a key ecosystem for information processing and retrieval. This culture played a pivotal role in shaping twentieth-century modernity. In this context, I analyze a range of programs that provide an on-screen simulacrum of a literal desktop, such as *Magic Desk* (Commodore, 1983). More broadly, I also explore ideas about how users should organize information processing on a computer, drawing inspiration from traditional office culture.

4. How user interfaces are represented in other media?

This focal point deconstructs the conventions and cultural logic behind the presentation of UIs in audiovisual media. Television programs from the 1980s, such as BBC's *The Mighty Micro* and *Micro Live*, often portrayed computers as the future, extensively showcasing actions on a computer screen to support their overarching theses on how computers would transform society. The highly influential program *Computer Chronicles* frequently employed the convention of inviting software designers into the studio, where they demonstrated program functionalities and discussed their qualities while navigating the interface on-screen. Rather than simply using such materials as supplementary sources for studying interfaces, I am more interested in exploring the cultural logic of speaking about and showcasing interfaces in other media.

This focal point also includes an investigation into the world of FUIs—fictional, or fantasy user interfaces. These are elaborate interfaces designed for audiovisual media to depict how users interact with computer technology in fictional settings.

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